

THE ROLE OF THE INTERPHASE IN COMPRESSIVE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

James Lankford¹
Arthur Nicholls¹
John Lesko²

¹Materials Development Department
Southwest Research Institute, San Antonio, Texas

²Engineering Science and Mechanics Department
Virginia Polytechnic Institute, Blacksburg, Virginia

ABSTRACT

The results of mesoindentation experiments involving graphite/epoxy composites of varying interphase shear strength (ISS) are described. It is found that kink band nucleation is relatively independent of ISS, while subcritical kink band growth apparently is controlled by the ISS. This finding appears to provide a physical basis for the ISS-dependent uniaxial compressive strength of these composites.

INTRODUCTION

Two different macroscopic failure modes are commonly observed for unidirectionally reinforced composites [1]. In the first case, if the bond between fiber and matrix is weak, transverse forces generated by Poisson's ratio mismatches can initiate fracture at the fiber/matrix interface and induce longitudinal splitting. Since most engineering composite systems involve fairly strong interfaces, this usually is not the dominant mode of failure.

More common, and the focus of this paper, is the observation of compression failure via shear crippling [1], which is associated with fiber buckling and kinking. This results in the production of kink bands, which usually lie at an angle of 20°-30° relative to the plane normal to the fibers. For graphite and E-glass reinforced systems, the kink band boundary usually is demarked by fiber fracture within a basically continuous polymer matrix.

Most models to describe compressive failure have been derived from the work of Rosen [2], who first analyzed the elastic buckling of perfectly aligned fibers. Subsequent variations on this theme [3-6] have resulted in predicted primary dependence on matrix shear strength and initial fiber misalignment, which has been validated experimentally. However, these analyses generally fail to predict the absolute failure strength, since they do not really predict kinking; they either represent the maximum compressive stress corresponding to buckling stability, following which kinking occurs as a post-failure event, or kinks are presumed to pre-exist (a physically unrealistic assumption). While it is clear that some buckling deformation must precede compressive failure,

recent experiments and observations indicate that compressive failure is triggered by localized damage mechanisms superimposed on an otherwise stable buckled state.

Recent work has shown, surprisingly in view of the theories just cited, that the fiber-matrix interphase also has significant influence on compressive strength. Swain, *et al.* [7], for example, have varied interphase properties while maintaining other parameters essentially constant. Compressive strength within the kink-band regime increased significantly with interfacial shear strength (ISS). Similarly, increasing the ISS produced dramatic increases in the high cycle life and fatigue limit for cyclic compression (Figure 1) [8], where failure again was via kink band nucleation and growth.

Figure 1. Compressive fatigue strength versus cycles for center-notched 0°/90° graphite epoxies of varying ISS.

The present paper represents an attempt to utilize a new technique, mesoindentation, to obtain insight as to the micromechanics by which the interphase manifests in compressive kink band nucleation and/or growth. The results of the experiments, which constitute an essentially confined compression test amenable to localized, stable kink development, will be interpreted in terms of implication for unconfined, macroscopic, uniaxial compressive failure.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Two graphite/epoxy systems of nominally identical properties other than their ISS values were selected for study. Preparation is described elsewhere [7]; material properties are shown in Table 1. For purposes of discussion, the materials are denoted as S and W for their strong and weak ISS values, respectively.

Table 1. Material Properties

Material	Compressive Strength (MPa)	ISS (MPa)
S	1664	> 67.0
W	908	57.3

Small samples were sectioned from composite panels, and embedded in metallographic mounting compound with the fibers nominally normal to the polishing plane. The specimens were polished metallographically using a 0.05 μm alumina slurry, producing a smooth finish for both matrix and fiber ends, and little fiber relief.

Mesoindentation testing was performed by monitoring load (P) while pressing a 1.58 mm diameter hardened steel ball under displacement control (6 $\mu\text{m/s}$) into the surface of the sample. Details have been given by Lesko, *et al.* [9]. The present tests differed from the latter principally in that simple crosshead displacement (d) rather than an LVDT relative to the indenter head and the sample surface was used as a measure of indenter penetration.

Indentations in samples loaded to various points along P-d curves were photographed, and subsequently sectioned and polished. Subsurface damage was likewise photographed, and correlated with indent surface features.

RESULTS

Shown in Figures 2 and 3 are representative load-displacement plots for the two composites. Duplicate experiments for both materials exhibit an initial convex P-d dependence, transiting suddenly at $P \approx 2.5$ kg to a linear relationship. At a load of about 4.0 kg, each curve abruptly undergoes a small jump in displacement, before settling back into an approximately linear P-d relationship. These results are summarized in the form of composite (data) curves for both materials in Figure 4. It can be seen that the two curves are virtually identical until the second "transition" (point B), above which displacements for a given load are consistently greater for the W material.

Figure 2. Indentation load versus penetrator displacement for S material; duplicate experiments are shown.

Figure 3. Indentation load versus penetrator displacement for W material; duplicate experiments are shown.

Figure 4. Combined P-d results for duplicate tests of S and W Materials.

At various points along these curves, the indentations that result display certain consistent characteristics. Shown in Figure 5a are indentations in the S material for $P = 4.5$ kg and $P = 7.15$ kg; each is characterized by a dark convex zone arcing around one side of the indent, within an overall circular impression. Sectioning through these indentations along the $x-x'$ plane reveals kink bands (Figure 5b) oriented asymmetrically relative to the centers of the indentations indicated by the arrows (the impression diameter, kink band length scaled consistently with P).

(a) Indentation impressions for $P = 4.5$ kg (left) and $P = 7.15$ kg (right).

(b) Subsurface kinks relative to indent centers (arrows) along section $x-x'$.

Figure 5. Indentation damage in S material.

It should be noted that within a given sample, the dark zone always was centered in the same sector of each indent, as shown in Figure 5a. Comparing Figures 5a and 5b, it is obvious that the dark zone represents the intersection of the subsurface kink band with the surface, which tilts the ends of the fibers so that they reflect light away from the lens, and thus appear darker.

The W material behaves similarly, as shown in Figure 6. In addition, it can be seen that for nominally identical loads in excess of point B (Figure 5, $P = 7.15$ kg, and Figure 6), the impression diameter is greater and subsurface kink length is longer for the W material. This correlates with the $P-d$ trend shown in Figure 4, i.e., greater indentation displacement in the W material than in the S composite at an equivalent load. These data are also consistent with those observed by Lesko, *et al.* [10] where kink band length was found to decrease with increasing

(a) Indentation impression for $P = 7.02$ kg.

(b) Subsurface kink relative to indent center (arrow) along section y - y' .

Figure 6. Indentation damage in W material.

compression strength (as influenced by interphase properties). Finally, it was observed that although impressions are formed between points A and B (Figure 4), they differ strikingly (for both materials) from impressions made with loads above point B. In particular, the dark convex zone is absent. Figure 7 shows such an impression (a) in the W material, versus a companion indent (b) caused by a load in excess of transition point B.

Figure 7. Indentations in W material at (a) $P = 3.52$ kg and (b) $P = 7.02$ kg, i.e., below and above transition point B, respectively.

DISCUSSION

Two issues will be considered here. First, what is the relationship between indentation kink band development and the load-displacement curve? Second, what are the implications of this relationship for uniaxial compressive failure of a bulk composite?

Since the only observed indentation damage mode (other than overall plastic flow) is subsurface kink banding, it is highly likely that the P-d break at point A (Figure 4) is caused by kink band nucleation. However, since the dark zone is absent between A and B, the suspect kink band must have nucleated subsurface. This is supported by the micromechanical analysis by Lesko, *et al.* [9], of the stress distribution beneath a spherical indenter during mesoindentation of a fiber-reinforced composite; in this case, the maximum shear stress is localized within a subsurface annular zone centered about the load axis. In addition, sectioning of indentations such as "a" in Figure 7 revealed fiber fractures that were compatible with kink band development. However, since plastic recovery was so complete for these small indents, fiber shear (kink) offsets such as those of Figures 5 and 6 could not be established with certainty.

Following kink nucleation at A (Figure 4), the band evidently grows with increasing load, contributing additional displacement to that controlled by indentation plasticity, and accounting for the lowering of the P-d slope. The kink zone probably grows principally toward the center of contact, since the indenter now serves to simply press down and rotate the near surface end of the kink band, i.e., the kink process is displacement rather than shear stress-driven. When the band reaches the surface, broken fiber elements evidently are destabilized (point B, Figure 4), rotating about the indenter to produce the "dark" zone within the contact zone, and generating a sudden increment in displacement. The orientation of the dark zone must reflect the original overall misalignment of the average fiber direction relative to the load axis. This misalignment predisposes the fibers to kink in a certain direction, hence the constancy of the dark zone orientation.

Displacement beyond point B (Figure 4) reflects stable, subcritical kink band propagation, now driven by a maximum shear stress criterion. In fact, the curved path of the kink band follows the locus of the maximum shear stress predicted by Lesko, *et al.* [9] for a steadily penetrating

indenter. It is this process that reflects the influence of the interphase, in terms of the greater displacement rate of the W material versus the S material (Figure 4).

Finally, the implications for compressive strength are as follows. Under compression loading, kink band nucleation probably is not affected by the interphase; nucleation requires a transition from broken to unbroken fibers, at which point disbonding, controlled by the interphase shear strength, can occur [11]. Subsequent subcritical prefailure development of the kink band is a growth process, driven by the local shear stress, with its rate controlled by the ISS. Failure occurs when the combination of kink band length and applied stress correspond to the critical kink stress intensity [6]. Since the rate of kink band extension for a given stress is lower for a material with a strong interphase than with a weak one, the weak interphase material will always attain the critical failure configuration at a lower applied compressive stress level than that required to fail a composite with a high ISS.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for the support of the Office of Naval Research under contract numbers N00014-95-C-0025 and N00014-95-1-0340.

REFERENCES

1. H. T. Hahn and J. G. Williams, Compression Failure mechanisms in unidirectional composites, *Composite Materials: Testing and Design*, ASTM STP 893, edited by J. M. Whitney, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 115-139 (1986).
2. B. W. Rosen, Mechanics of composite strengthening, *Fiber Composite Materials*, American Society of Metals, Metals Park, OH, 37-45 (1964).
3. A. S. Argon, treatise on materials science and technology, vol. 1 (Academic Press, NY, 1972).
4. B. Budiansky, Micromechanics, *Computers and Structures*, **16**, 3-12 (1983).
5. B. Budiansky and N. A. Fleck, Compressive failure of fiber composites, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, **41**, 183-211 (1993).
6. M.P.F. Sutcliffe and N.A. Fleck, Microbuckle propagation in carbon fibre-epoxy composites, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, **42**, 2219-2231 (1994).
7. R. E. Swain, J. S. Elmore, J. J. Lesko, and K. L. Reifsnider, The role of fiber, matrix, and interphase in the compressive static and fatigue behavior of polymeric matrix composite laminates, *Compression Response of Composite Structures*, ASTM STP 1185, eds., S. E. Groves and A. L. Highsmith, ASTM, Philadelphia, 205-277 (1994).
8. J. J. Lesko, The influence of interphase properties on the compression mechanics of polymer composites, Ph.D. Dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University (August, 1994).
9. J. J. Lesko, G. P. Carman, D. A. Dillard, and K. L. Reifsnider, Meso-indentation testing of composite materials as a tool for measuring interfacial quality, *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture*, ASTM STP 1156, eds., W. W. Stinchcomb and N. E. Ashbaugh, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 401-418 (1993).
10. J. J. Lesko, J. S. Elmore, S. W. Case, R. E. Swain, K. L. Reifsnider, and D. A. Dillard, A global and local investigation of compressive strength to determine the influence of the fiber/matrix interphase, *Compression Response of Composite Structures*, ASTM STP 1185, eds., S. E. Groves and A. L. Highsmith, ASTM, Philadelphia, 228-240 (1994).
11. J. Lankford, Compressive failure of fiber-reinforced composites: buckling, kinking, and the role of the interphase, *J. Mat. Sci.* (in press).